

was refluxed with acrylamide (1.2 g) ($AlCl_3$ added as catalyst) for 20 min. Usual work up and chromatographic separation afforded **2** (375 mg) and **3** (450 mg) which were found identical (m.p., tlc, ir and nmr) with those obtained by the reaction of the epoxide **1** with phenylisocyanate.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor M. S. Ahmad, Chairman, Department of Chemistry for providing facilities.

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Mass Spectral Studies of some Fluorinated Indoles and Benzindoles

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Manuscript received 10 September 1986, accepted 2 August 1986

IN continuation to our attempts in exploring the synthetic applications of some arsonium and pyridinium ylides¹⁻⁹, we recently reported the synthesis of some new fluorinated indoles and benzindoles through pyridinium ylides¹⁰. We now report the mass spectral studies of some fluorinated indoles (**1-4**) and benzindoles (**5, 6**).

Experimental

The m.p., ir and pmr spectra of some new fluorinated indoles and benzindoles through pyridinium ylides have been reported¹⁰. The mass spectra were taken on a MC-30 mass spectrometer with direct inlet system.

Results and Discussion

The compounds **1** and **2** having methyl group in 5-position show a similar fragmentation pattern (Scheme 1). In the case of compounds **3** and **4**, an important fragmentation occurs around ethoxy group (Scheme 2).

The indole nucleus is reported¹¹ to show little fragmentation and our results are in its close accordance. As expected, the molecular ion peak of indoles forms the base peak in the spectrum. It has been reported¹² that introduction of alkyl substituents into the indole system results in the α,β -cleavage and hence a prominent M-1 peak in the spectrum. Thus, compounds **1** and **2** show M-1 peaks at m/e 224 (**2a**, 70.3%) and 238 (**2b**, 65.7%), respectively. The resulting ion **2** is expected to undergo ring expansion¹³ to form the ion **2'** which subsequently loses

(3, 7–16%). This is in accordance with the loss of HCN from M-1 peak in the case of 2-methylindole^{1a}. The ion 3 splits off acetylene molecule to give the ion 4 at m/e 77. Further, an ion (5) of m/e 130 (5.6–5.8%) is observed in the mass spectra of both 1 and 2. This ion obviously results from the parent ion by the loss of 2-aryl group. Ion 5 subsequently leads to the ion 6 at m/e 102 (10.6–12.4%). Our results indicate that in the case of 7-ethoxyindoles (3 and 4), the initial fragmentation occurs around the ethoxy group. Thus, the molecular ion 7 which forms the base peak, loses ethane or ethanol moieties to form the ions 8 and 9, respectively, at appropriate mass units. The ion 8 eliminates formyl radical, like phenols,

to form an ion at m/e 77. The molecular ion may also lose ethoxy radical to form the ion 11.

Benzindoles show a similar behaviour like indoles and the only appreciable fragmentation results by the loss of HCN from the parent ion which forms the base peak^{1a}. In the case of 2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1*H*-benz[*g*]indole (5) and 2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-3*H*-benz[*e*]indole (6), the molecular

ions (12 and 13, respectively) lose $\text{N}\equiv\text{C}-$

to give the ion 14 at m/e 140. A peak at m/e 139 may be attributed to the ion 15 formed from the ion 14 by the loss of a hydrogen atom. This is in accordance with the results obtained in connection with the mass spectral studies of 2-carboxybenz[*e*]indole^{1a}. The ion 15 does not undergo further fragmentation as the fused ring systems are resistant to mass fragmentation. The mass spectra of these two benzindoles exhibited a peak at m/e 130.5 which corresponds to the doubly charged ion (Scheme 3)

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, for

providing facilities. One of the authors (S. M.) expresses her gratitude to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support.

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Reaction of 2-Hydroxydibenzoylmethanes with Hydroxylamine Hydrochloride in DMF-Water. Dielectric Constant Dependent Products: Isoxazole and Benzisoxazole

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Manuscript received 6 May 1985, revised 1 January 1986, accepted 2 August 1986

ISOXAZOLE derivatives are well known as anti-bacterial¹, antitubercular², antiviral³, antifungal⁴, anticonvulsants⁵, and corrosion inhibitors for fuels and lubricants⁶. Lohiya⁷ in his recent work established that some of the previous workers had mistaken benzisoxazole derivative (it does not give ferric chloride colour due to absence of free phenolic OH group) as isoxazole. The benzisoxazole forms along with isoxazole (gives ferric chloride colour reaction) in DMF and aqueous DMF medium from 2-hydroxy-dibenzoylmethane derivative with hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

The present investigation deals with the reaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride on some dibenzoylmethane derivatives (β -diketones) in DMF, DMF-water mixture and *N*-methylacetamide media; isolation of the products, isoxazole and benzisoxazole, and their formation ratio. An attempt has been made to explain the ratio of formation of